

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B037
 Date: 31 Jul 2004
 Take Off: 09:52:41
 Landing: 15:13:39
 Flight Time: 5h20m58

Trials Instructions: ITOP – interception OF north American outflow previously sampled by P3
Operating Area: North-West of the Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Reeves	UEA
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	ORAC/PAN/TDL/PSAP	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
9	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
10	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
11	WAS	Debbie Wylding	UEA
12	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
13	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
14	FAGE	Cedric Floquet	Leeds University
15	Mission Scientist 2	Steve Arnold	Leeds University
16	Observer	James Levine	Cambridge University
17	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
18			

Track Plot:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B037
 Date: 31st July 2004
 Project: ITOP - N American plume
 Location: Azores, N of LUKAL and LUKIT

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095241		T/O	8.4 kft	299	from Horta
095745	100137	Run 1	9.0 - 9.4 kft	298	
100843	112254	Run 2	14.0 kft	294	
101651		Videos	14.0 kft	295	Start recording
112313	114840	Profile 1	14.0 - 0.95 kft	352	500fpm
114958	115857	Profile 2	0.93 - 5.0 kft	067	500fpm
115910	121210	Run 3	5.0 kft	076	
121228	121753	Profile 3	5.0 - 7.5 kft	084	Spiral climb
122038	123550	Run 4	7.5 kft	269	
123550	124307	Profile 4	7.5 - 11.5 kft	272	500fpm
124506	130007	Run 5	11.5 kft	099	
130133	130633	Run 6	11.5 kft	162	
130807	131458	Profile 5	11.5 - 14.5 kft	248	500fpm, interrupt
131710	132212	Profile 5	14.5 - 17.0 kft	070	turn onto to E
1323		HORACE CRASHED			
132340	133027	Run 7	17.0 kft	185	
133027	133444	Profile 6	17.0 - 19.0 kft	187	
133503	141625	Run 8	19.0 kft	184	
132400		Videos	19.0 kft	185	change tapes
141625	141821	Profile 7	17.3 - 17.1 kft	185	
141833	143835	Run 9	17.0 kft	148	
144332	144527	Run 10	7.0 kft	128	7200ft,1021mb abeam Pico
145502	145703	Run 11	6.3 kft	305	6500ft abeam Pico
150159	150400	Run 12	5.3 kft	127	5500ft abeam Pico
151339		Land	-.14 kft	087	at Horta

B037 Track 31-JUL-04

Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Position
 Present position (hours and minutes)
 Flight level
 Position on assigned route or OCA entry point
 Time for next position or OCA entry point
 Next position
 Whether FL acceptable or requested at Position or Time
 Other information e.g. MET data or company message
ARRANCE:
 Request with a routine position report, to request a change of
 Altitude, Flight Level, or route and to request Westbound
 Clearance prior to entering Reykjavik, Santa Maria and
 Azores.
 Data sequence:
 "Clearance"
 Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Present position
 Present or last reported position (hours and minutes)
 Flight Level
 Position on assigned route or OCA entry point
 Time for next position or OCA entry point
 Next position
 Mach Number, Flight Level, or route
 Information or clarifying remarks
 Change in Mach Number, or route when a position report
 is appropriate.
 Data sequence:
 "Clearance"
 Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Mach Number, or route
 Information or clarifying remarks
ESTIMATE:
 Estimate for next position.
 Data sequence:
 "Estimate"
 Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Position or route
 Estimate for next position (hours and minutes)
 Information
CLIMB:
 Information on position or time a climb to the next higher FL is
 requested. Clearance for higher FLs is requested when inclusion in
 message is not appropriate.
 Data sequence:
 Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Mach Number or Acceptable FLs
 Time or time
TEXT MESSAGE:
 Information on or make a request in plain language that does not
 contain content of other message format. No message
 is inserted as this will be inserted by the ground station.
 Data sequence:
 Notification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Information or request in plain language and format free.

ALTIMETER SETTING
 Standard pressure setting for cruising flights
 OCEANIC FIRs. QNH setting on descent
 transition levels.

OCEANIC CTA/KZNY FIR
 (1 below FL55)
 AIRSPACE FL290-FL410
 SANTA MARIA OCEANIC
 CTA/LPPO FIR(G)
 (1 below FL55)
 AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA RADIO	
NAT A	NAT E
3016	2962
5598	6628
8906	8825
13306	11309
17946	17946
VHF	
127.90	132.07
SELCAL	
① 426302	

① SATCOM Air-to-Ground
 COM-failure.

B037: ITOP – Interception of North American previously sampled by P3.

Mission Scientists: Claire Reeves & Steve Arnold

Date: 31/07/04

Outline schedule:

06:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

08:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing

09:15 UT – Security sweep

09:30 UT – Boarding deadline

10:00 UT - Take-off

Location: North-west of the Azores

Aim: To intercept polluted plume which left US east coast in a warm conveyor belt. This air has been sampled twice previously by the P3 on the 27th and 28th. Comparison with Pico, in particular VOCs (in situ and bottles).

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to first available level for wet chemistry checks. (10)
2. T+10 ~~Ascend~~ Ascend to FL140 and transit to LUKAL (41 15N, 32 21W). Include at least 20 mins level in clear air for calcs. (60)
3. T+70 Enter operating area, turn to northwest and profile descend to 100ft @ 500ft/min through polluted filament (30)
4. T+100 Turn eastwards and profile ascend to level of max. pollution at 500ft/min (15).
5. T+125 Turn onto northwest heading and perform level run (20).
6. T+145 Turn reciprocal and perform level run to plume maximum (15)
7. T+160 Turn towards northeast and perform level run. (15)
8. T+175 Profile to second level of interest @500ft/min. (5).
9. T+180 Reciprocal turn, and perform level run on southwest heading (15).
10. T+195 Reciprocal, then profile ascent to next level @ 500ft/min. (10)
11. T+205 Level run to northeast along filament orientation (15).
12. T+220 Profile ascend to FL170 for transit home via LUKAL (or LUKIT) (10)
13. T+230 Transit back to Azores. Include 20 mins level run (out of cloud) (55) FL170
14. T+285 Perform racetrack around Pico for comparison with ground obs at 7200 ft (and other levels if time allows) (20) + 5500ft.
15. T+305 Return to Horta.
16. T+315 Land.

New plot, same times

Flight B037 15:03:44

Heading 124 deg Speed 212 knots Height 5.2kft Press 834mb

Lat 38.4N Long 28.3W Wind 12 ms-1/ 308 deg

Temp 14.87C Dewpoint 7.17C

From 14:43:32 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	54222	secs	☒ All
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	89.06	%	☐
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	48.89	ppb	☐
—	CO MIXING RATIO	81.67	ppb	☐

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...037.....

Date ...31.7.04.....

Page ...1... of

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS ☒
(V8)		Lat	41° 57.41N	41° 58.21N
No.		Long	32° 19.21W	32° 19.86W
Ends		Time	11:08:52	11:09:26
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓	NAV
				HORACE ☒ <i>2 crashes pit</i>
				SATCOM ☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
095241	TAKE	off from	Horsta.					
095745	start	run	1	vet	chew			
100137	End	Run 1.						
100843		R2						112254
112313	START	P1 ↓	500'/min	FL10.	⊙	1000ft		114840
114958		P2 ↑						115857
115910		R3						121210
121228		P3 ↑	turning					121753
122038	FLT5	R4						
132001	End	run						
133027	st	Profile 6					133464	170 ↓ Lokit
1437	Jim McQuarrel - Satcom H phone call to Pico site otherwise all calls pos rpt from Haynar.							
151339	Land	at Horsta.		sh 20				1510-ETA
					GPS Shutdown + Startup Posn.			
					28 38° 31. 26N			
					28° 42 .98W			
1545								

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.037**.....

Date **31.7.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		/	FFSSP	X	
Satcom C			PCASP	X	
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	X	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	X	
De-Iced Temp		/	Cloudscope	X	
Non De-Iced			SID 1	X	
Heimann		✓	SID 2	X	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		
G. Eastern		/	HVPS		
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	x		INC	x	
TWC			CCN / CNC		FWVS only
FWVS		✓	CVI	x	
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
" Red			PSAP		✓
" Silicon		JN02 /	Nephelometer	x	
" JO1D			AMS		✓
Lower Clear					
" Red					
" Silicon		JN02 /			
" JO1D		✓			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHIM	X				
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		/			
ECGC					
NOX					
CO			<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC					
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS		✓			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. 6037

Instruments

1. HORACE crashed twice on preflight. 2nd time coincided with making CBS for eorcon anti-icing panel.
2. CAMERAS: no aft facing picture
no upward picture until after t/o.
- 2a. Clitches on NDI, DI, JW, Press Height on P/f, reset Core DU
3. Pressure Height started reading 0.0 in flight @ 1300 ft
reset PAFT DU then okay. Airspeed was okay at this time.
4. Upper BBRs - spikes on Red signal not evident on clear.
5. HORACE crashed in flight 1323
6. FFC window froze over during flight as we skimmed cloud top -11.8°C . Remained frozen for $\frac{3}{4}$ hr

Aircraft